

INVOLVING STUDENTS IN ASSESSMENT VIA PEER- AND SELF-ASSESSMENT

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It is recognized that the essential aim of professional higher education is to help students develop into reflective practitioners who are able to reflect critically upon their own professional practice. To engage students in the learning process and to encourage them to take responsibility for their own learning requires the involvement of students in the assessment process. Students' participation in the assessment process enhances the development of essential skills, such as responsibility, judgement and autonomy which have a considerable importance for their professional career and life. Taking part in assessment gives substantial opportunity to students for developing self-regulating skills.

Involvement of students in assessment can take place in two ways: self- and

peer-assessment. Self-evaluation refers to the involvement of learners in making judgements about their own learning, particularly, about their achievements and outcomes of their learning. As a result of self-assessment students learn to identify specific actions they need to take to improve and to plan next steps. That is, they define their long-term and short-term goals with increasing confidence. Self-assessment may change the nature of the interaction and relationship between teachers and students. Through self-assessment, teachers can understand and monitor their students' understanding, use of strategy and effective states. This in turn allows teachers to open a dialogue and facilitate interaction with students during instruction. When self-assessment incorporated into the

learning process in an educational environment, the level of students' motivation can be strengthened.¹ Moreover, self-assessment helps students to develop essential metacognitive skills that contribute to a range of vital graduate capabilities, increases self-awareness through reflective practice, making the criteria for self-evaluation explicit, and making performance improvement practices intrinsic to ongoing learning. Falchikov defines peer assessment as the process whereby groups of individuals rate their peers.² Peer evaluation is a practice that can foster high levels of responsibility among students; the students must be fair and accurate with the judgements they make regarding their peers. Peer assessment emphasizes skills, encourages involvement, concentrates on learning, creates a reference, promotes excellence, provides increased feedback, fosters attendance and teaches responsibility. Conway indicates that learners found group projects more engaging than traditional methods of teaching.

In peer evaluation students rate their peers' work and have their work assessed by peers. Often implemented as a learning implement, peer assessment provides students feedback on the quality of their work, often with advice and strategies for enhancement. Simultaneously, judging peers' work can improve the evaluators' own learning and self-esteem. Peer involvement personalizes the learning experience, potentially motivating continuous learning. Peer assessment approaches differ significantly, and are often best comprehended via practice. To provide efficient, valid and trusty feedback to fellow learners, students require accurate instructions, practicing on rating criteria and rating rules and train with models. Before students get prepared to give feedback to others, their assessments ought to be assimilated to staff-grading of the equal samples for quality assurance. Results of the research investigating the perceptions of students about peer-assessment show that a very positive attitude towards using peer evaluation.³ Researchers report that implementing self- and/or peer-

assessment have positive influences on students' perceptions. It can be concluded that the use of self- and peer-assessment are necessary to

remove the student-tutor barrier, to develop enterprising competencies in students and can lead to greater motivation and deeper learning.

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